

Minutes EB26-1
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
27 February 2026

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apologies

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

SeqCode Prize
Annual Report

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

1. *FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved. Completed*
2. *IS to initiate the discussion of the proposed changes to the SeqCode on the Slack channel once the manuscript has been accepted for publication. Completed*
3. *KK to provide suggestion for minimum metadata recommendations for consideration by the board members. To be shared with EB*
4. *FV to contact the ISME office to request assistance with the Vice-Chair voting process. Ongoing*
5. *LMR to investigate the possible options and processes to obtain legal protection for the SeqCode name. Ongoing*
6. *LMR and BW to prepare and submit a funding application for 2026 to the ISME office. Ongoing*
7. *FV to request ISME to consider waiving the publication costs of manuscripts related to the operation of the SeqCode in ISME Communications. ISME Board approved two publications per year.*

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The public discussion of the paratype proposal was initiated on the Slack channel and will be open until the end of April.

As decided earlier, additional proposals to amend the SeqCode will be collected and combined in a single proposal to fully utilize the free publications in ISME Communications. The next set of amendments will include recognition of the ranks of Domain and Kingdom.

Standards Working Group

KK discussed the minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries of genome sequences with LMR. They will circulate suggestions on how the required and recommended data quality requirements linked to the SeqCode should be amended to formalize these requirements.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 1247 names have been validated, which include those of 666 species. LMR also indicated that the registry needs nomenclature support as there are 2255 names currently under review. An additional 425 names have also been endorsed and awaiting publication to become validated. Assistance with the review of names is still required.

The creation of Latin names remains one of the main hurdles for scientists planning to name new taxa. LMR will follow-up with Thomas Hitch about the possible use of Protologger for the naming of taxa using GAN or similar programs.

Reconciliation Commission

The commission has not met since the last EB meeting and has nothing to report.

5. Election of new Vice-Chair

The ISME office will soon send out the ballot to all members of the SeqCode community.

6. Election of the Executive Board

A new Executive Board should be elected as the term of the current board will end in December 2026. IS indicated that the following officers should be elected:

Members of the Executive Board

Executive Board Chair
Executive Board Vice-Chair
Executive Board Secretary
Executive Board Member without Portfolio (optional)
Executive Board Member without Portfolio (optional)
Legislative Commission Chair
Reconciliation Commission Chair
Registry & Nomenclature Working Group Chair
Standards Working Group Chair

Other members of commissions or working groups

Legislative Commission Vice-Chair
Legislative Commission Secretary
Legislative Commission Additional Member (and optional Additional Member)
Reconciliation Commission Vice-Chair
Reconciliation Commission Secretary
Reconciliation Commission Additional Member
Reconciliation Commission up to 4 other Additional Members
Registry & Nomenclature Working Group Secretary
Standards Working Group Secretary

A call for nominations will be circulated as part of the next SeqCode News, which will be distributed in March. The call will remain open until after ISME20, which will be held in Auckland, New Zealand (16–21 August 2026). This conference provides an ideal opportunity to promote the SeqCode, an ISME-supported initiative. It will also offer a valuable platform to recruit new members interested in joining the community and becoming involved in the management of the SeqCode. The final slate of candidates will be confirmed in September. Elections will be held around early/mid-October to ensure that the incoming officers are announced before the end of 2026.

Based on Statute 4.2, SeqCode Community members will need to reconfirm their membership before 01 January 2027. A reminder of this requirement will be sent to members later in the year.

7. Scheduling of plenary meeting of the SeqCode Community

A plenary meeting of the SeqCode Community should be held once during the four-year term of the Executive Board. The BISMIS Executive will be approached to inquire if the BISMIS Live slot of September 2026 could be used for this purpose. Suggestions for the format of the meeting will be presented at the next EB meeting by a small committee consisting of MC, IS and FV.

8. SeqCode Prize

The ISME office will be contacted urgently to investigate the possibility of awarding the SeqCode prize at the ISME20 meeting. The administrative assistance to be provided by the ISME office will also be clarified.

9. Annual report

The chairs of the commissions and working groups are requested to provide a short report on their activities for 2025. The reports should reach BW before the end of March.

10. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to submit any relevant documents on the shared drive.

(https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1bH4Sluh3kjC9YM8CTqUn1T-q5c1kED7HvJLu_wNf2Pk/edit#gid=0)

New action items

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. FV to send out a call for nominations of officials for the next term as part of the SeqCode News.
3. LMR will follow-up with Thomas Hitch about the possible use of Protologger for the naming of taxa.
4. FV to approach the BISMIS Executive to inquire if the BISMIS Live slot of September 2026 could be used for hosting the SeqCode plenary.
5. MC, IS and FV to provide suggestions for the format of the SeqCode Community plenary meeting.
6. IS, KK, LMR and MC to provide a short report on the activities of commissions and working groups for 2025. The reports should reach BW before the end of March.

Ongoing items

7. LMR and BW to prepare and submit a funding application for 2026 to the ISME office, including funding for the SeqCode prize
8. FV to follow-up with the ISME office regarding the Vice-Chair voting process.
9. LMR to investigate the possible options and processes to obtain legal protection for the SeqCode name.
10. KK and LMR to share suggestion for minimum metadata recommendations for consideration by the board members.

Minutes prepared by FV: 1 Mach 2026

Approved: 15 March 2026